

New predatory flies associated with *Orthotomicus erosus* (Wollaston) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) in Bulgaria

Sevdalin Belilov^{1,2}, Mihail Kechev^{2,3}, Georgi Georgiev^{2,4}

(1) Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St. Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, wea.sevdo@gmail.com

(2) Center of Competence “AgriFood Systems and Bioeconomy”, 26 Maritsa Street, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

(3) Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St. Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, mkechev@gmail.com

(4) [Corresponding author] Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St. Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, ggeorgiev.fri@gmail.com

Abstract: In May 2024, stem cuttings of *Pinus sylvestris* L. attacked by the first generation of *Orthotomicus erosus* (Wollaston) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) were collected in the Vladimir Village area in Southwestern Bulgaria. The samples were transported to the Laboratory of Entomology at Forest Research Institute in Sofia. The cuttings were placed in photoelectors and were kept at room temperature (18–22°C). Four predatory dipteran species, *Medetera pinicola* (Kowarz), *M. signaticornes* (Loew) (Diptera: Dolichopodidae), *Lonchaea collini* Hackman (Diptera: Lonchaeidae) and *Zabrachia tenella* (Jaenicke) (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) were reared for the first time from larval galleries of *O. erosus*. Two species (*Medetera signaticornes* and *Zabrachia tenella*) are new for the fauna of Bulgaria. The genus *Zabrachia* is also new to Bulgarian fauna. In this study, the finding of the species with northern distribution *M. signaticornes* is the second record on Balkan Peninsula.

Keywords: *Lonchaea collini*, *Medetera pinicola*, *Medetera signaticornes*, new records, predator-prey associations, *Zabrachia tenella*

Introduction

Orthotomicus erosus (Wollaston, 1857) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) is very common bark beetle infesting all pines (*Pinus* spp.), and rarely *Cedrus atlantica* Carrière and *Cedrus libani* A.Rich. (Lieutier et al., 2016). According to the authors, the species is naturally distributed in Central and Southern Europe including Atlantic and British Islands, North Africa, Western and Central Asia until China and Korea and is introduced in Northern Europe, South Africa, Chile, Fiji Islands and the United States. *O. erosus* is mainly a secondary species that develop on trees attacked by bark beetles that are more aggressive but in high population levels, it attacks healthy trees. Mendel & Halperin (1982) identified *O. erosus* as the main species involved in bark beetle outbreaks, killing large numbers of planted *Pinus halepensis* (Mill.) and *Pinus brutia* (Ten.) in Northern and Central Israel. Jiang et al.

(1992) reported *O. erosus* as an aggressive primary pest that attacks and kills healthy trees of *Pinus massoniana* Lambert in China.

In Bulgaria, *O. erosus* is common among the complex of bark beetle in pine stands and plantations in Southwestern Bulgaria, the Rhodope Mountains, Balkan Range and Sakar Mountain (Doychev, 2014). To date, no studies have been conducted on the biology and ecology of the species, including its parasitoids and predators.

The present study reports the first findings of predatory flies in larval galleries of *O. erosus* in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The biological material was collected on 10 and 28 May 2024 from a 50-year-old mixed plantation of *Pinus sylvestris* L. and *Pinus nigra* Arn., with average

diameter 20.0 cm and average height 14.0 m. The studied plantation is located in the Gradishte area near Vladimir Village, Radomir Region at geographical coordinates 42.446360°N, 23.084474°E, and altitude 800 m a.s.l.

The samples (stem cuttings of *P. sylvestris* with an approximate length 30–35 cm) were collected from five trees infested by the first generation of *Orthotomicus erosus* (Fig. 1).

The samples were transported to the Laboratory of Entomology at Forest Research Institute in Sofia, Bulgaria. The cuttings were placed in photoelectors and kept at room temperature (18–22°C). The samples were checked weekly and newly emerged predators were placed separately in 70% alcohol in plastic Eppendorf tubes for identification.

The emerged adults of the genus *Medetera* were identified by the keys of Parent (1938), Negrobov, Stackelberg (1969), d'Assis Fonseca (1978) and Bickel (1985). *Zabrachia tenella* was identified by the keys of Negrobov, Stackelberg (1969) and description of Beuk (1990), and *Lonchaea collini* – by the keys of Stackelberg (1970).

The biological material is housed in the entomological collection of the Forest Research Institute in Sofia.

Results

Dolichopodidae

Medetera pinicola (Kowarz, 1878)

Material: 17 June–28 July 2024, 7 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; leg. S. Belilov, det. M. Kechev.

Distribution: Holarctic species, occurring in Europe, South Russia (Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar), East Russia (Novosibirsk, Krasnoyarsk) (Grichanov, 2007), and North America (Rocky Mountains south to Arizona, northern Coast Ranges, boreal Canada, from Ungava south along Atlantic Coastal Plain and Appalachians to Georgia) (Bickel, 1985).

Habitat preference: Strictly confined to conifer trees of *Pinus* and *Picea* genera (Kenis et al., 2004).

Prey associations: The larvae live in galleries of bark beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) and feed on different stages of *Hylurgops palliatus* (Gyllenhal, 1813), *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758),

Fig. 1. Entrance holes and imago of *Orthotomicus erosus* on *Pinus sylvestris* tree.

Pityogenes chalcographus (Linnaeus, 1760), and *Tomicus* spp. (Kenis et al., 2004).

Medetera signaticornis (Loew, 1857) (Fig. 2)

Material: 28 June–3 July 2024, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; leg. S. Belilov, det. M. Kechev.

Distribution: Predominantly a Holarctic species with northern distribution, also occurring in the Oriental region (Pollet & Meuffels, 2023). Grichanov (2006) reported in great detail the range of *M. signaticornis* in Palaearctic, but Bulgaria was not included in the list of countries with distribution of the species in Europe. First record for Bulgaria.

Habitat preference: Strictly confined to conifer trees of *Picea* and *Pinus* genera (Kenis et al., 2004; Pollet & Meuffels, 2023).

Prey associations: The larvae live in galleries of bark beetles and feed on *Ips sexdentatus* (Boerner, 1776) and *I. typographus* (Kenis et al., 2004).

Lonchaeidae

Lonchaea collini Hackman, 1956

Material: 17 June 2024, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; leg. S. Belilov, det. M. Kechev.

Distribution: European species with northern distribution (MacGowan & Gustad, 2022; Hoem, 2026; Liljeblad, 2026).

Habitat preference: Confined to conifer trees (Kenis et al., 2004).

Fig. 2. *Medetera signaticornes*: A – habitus; B – head; C – hypopygium.

Fig. 3. Habitus of *Zabrachia tenella*.

Prey associations: The larvae live in galleries of bark beetles and feed on *Ips acuminatus* (Gyllenhal, 1827), *I. sexdentatus* and *Tomicus* spp. (Kenis et al., 2004).

Stratiomyidae

Zabrachia tenella (Jaenicke, 1866) (Fig. 3)

Material: 5–8 July 2024, 2 ♀♀; leg. S. Belilov, det. M. Kechev.

Distribution: Sweden, Germany, Former Czechoslovakia, Russia, the Netherlands, Belgium, France (Beuk, 1990). First record for Bulgaria.

Prey associations: The genus *Zabrachia* has been reported from larval galleries of *Ips typographus* (Kenis et al., 2004).

Discussion

Medetera pinicola, *M. signaticornis*, *Lonchaea collini* and *Zabrachia tenella* have not been previously found in the galleries of *O. erosus* (Kenis et al., 2004). Therefore, four new predator-prey associations were found in the present study.

The genus *Medetera* Fischer von Waldheim, 1819 (Diptera: Dolichopodidae), is one of the most species-rich genera in the family Dolichopodidae, comprising about 180 Palearctic species (Negrobov & Naglis, 2016). In Bulgaria, the genus *Medetera* is not well studied and only 16 species have been registered for the country (Kechev et al., 2020; Kechev, 2021a, 2021b).

The species of the genus *Medetera* are known as major predators of bark beetles and are of significant importance as biological control agents (Bickel, 1985). However, there is insufficient knowledge about the specificity to different scolytid species. In Bulgaria, only two species are known to be predators of scolytids: *M. pinicola* have been reared from the galleries of *Ips typographus* (Doychev et al., 2016), and *M. dendrobaena* Kowarz, 1877 – from the galleries of *Ips acuminatus* (Kechev et al., 2022).

Wermelinger (2002) indicated *M. signaticornis* as one of the most common predators of *I. typographus* in Switzerland. The species is with northern distribution, but it was also reported from Italy and Croatia in South Europe (Pollet & Ivković 2018). Thus, the present finding is the second report of *M. signaticornis* on Balkan Peninsula.

Lonchaea collini is known to the fauna of Bulgaria from Pamporovo (MacGowan et al., 2024). According to the authors, the larvae develop beneath the bark of recently dead conifers.

Until 1985, *Zabrachia tenella* was considered a synonym of *Zabrachia minutissima* (Zetterstedt, 1838) (Beuk, 1990). Krivosheina & Rozkošný (1985) studied the European *Zabrachia* and established that the material of *Z. minutissima* belonged to at least two species, and *Z. tenella* was withdrawn from synonymy. Beuk (1990) clearly distinguishes *Zabrachia tenella* from *Z. minutissima*. According to the description, the species we found in Bulgaria coincides with *Z. tenella*. The old reports of the finding of *Z. minutissima* in the larval galleries of *Ips typographus* before the revision of Krivosheina & Rozkošný (1985) have not been verified and may also be related to *Z. tenella*.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the new findings increase the richness of Bulgarian dipteran fauna and expand the knowledge on natural enemies of *Orthotomicus erosus*.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by project BG16RFPR002-1.014-0012-C01 “Establishment and sustainable development of a Center of Competence AgriFood Systems and Bioeconomy”, financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the “Program for Research, Innovation and Digitalisation for Smart Transformation” (PRIDST).

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As a member of the editorial board Mihail Kechev recused himself from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

Author's contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Sevdalin Belilov: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; Mihail Kechev: investigation, writing—original draft; Georgi Georgiev: investigation, methodology, project administration, writing—original draft.

References

- Beuk P.L.Th. 1990 The occurrence of *Zabrachia tenella* in the Netherlands (Diptera: Stratiomyidae). *Entomologische Berichten* 50 (8): 101–106.
- Bickel D.J. 1985 A Revision of the Nearctic *Medetera* (Diptera: Dolichopodidae). USDA Technical Bulletin No. 1692, 109 pp.
- d'Assis Fonseca E.C.M. 1978 Diptera Orthorrhapha Brachycera. V. Dolichopodidae. *Handbooks for the identification of British insects*. IX. Part 5: 1–90.
- Doychev D. 2014 Bark beetles (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Scolytinae) in plantations of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) in Southwestern Bulgaria – species composition, distribution and impact. PhD Thesis, University of Forestry, Sofia, Bulgaria, 192 pp. (In Bulgarian)
- Doychev D., Kechev M., Todorov I., Mirchev P., Bencheva S., Georgiev G. 2016 New Entomophagous Enemies of *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) from Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 68 (1): 131–134.
- Grihanov I.Y. 2006 A checklist and keys to North European genera and species of Dolichopodidae (Diptera). *Plant Protection News, Supplement*, St. Petersburg: VIZR RAAS, 120 pp.
- Grihanov I.Y. 2007 A checklist and keys to Dolichopodidae (Diptera) of the Caucasus and East Mediterranean. *VIZR RAAS, Plant Protection News, St. Petersburg, Supplement*, 160 pp.
- Hoem S. 2026 Norwegian Species Observation Service. Version 1.339. Norwegian Biodiversity Information Centre. Occurrence dataset. <https://doi.org/10.15468/zjazel>
- Jiang Y.P., Huang Z.Y., Huang X.C. 1992 Studies on *Orthotomicus erosus*. *Journal of Zhejiang University (Natural Sciences)* 15: 79–81.
- Kechev M. 2021a Diversity of long-legged flies (Diptera, Dolichopodidae) of the Balkan Mountains (Bulgaria and Serbia). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 42: 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.42.041>
- Kechev M. 2021b Data on the distribution of Dolichopodidae (Diptera: Empidoidea) in Bulgaria, with first records for the country. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 42: 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.42.131>

- Kechev M., Belilov S., Georgiev G. 2022 Two predatory *Medetera* (Diptera: Dolichopodidae) species associated with *Ips acuminatus* (Gyllenhal) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) in Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 44 (8): 63–67.
<https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.44.081>
- Kechev M., Naglis S., Tonguç A., Pollet M. 2020 Checklist of the Dolichopodidae (Diptera, Empidoidea) of the Balkan Peninsula, with first records for Bulgaria, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and for the European part of Turkey. *Zootaxa* 4819 (3): 436–472.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4819.3.2>
- Kenis M., Wermelinger B., Grégoire J.C. 2004 Research on Parasitoids and Predators of Scolytidae – A Review. In: Lieutier F., Day K.R., Battisti A., Grégoire J.-C., Evans H.F. (eds) *Bark and Wood Boring Insects in Living Trees in Europe, a Synthesis*. Dordrecht, London, Kluwer Academic, pp. 237–290.
- Krivosheina N.P., Rozkošný R. 1985 Additional notes on Palaearctic Pachygasterinae (Diptera, Stratiomyidae). *Acta Entomologica Bohemoslovaca* 82: 143–149.
- Lieutier F., Mendel Z., Faccoli M. 2016 Bark Beetles of Mediterranean Conifers. In: Paine T., Lieutier F. (eds) *Insects and Diseases of Mediterranean Forest Systems*. Springer, Cham, pp. 105–197.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24744-1_6
- Liljeblad J. 2026 Artportalen. Version 92.455. SLU Artdatabanken. Occurrence dataset.
<https://doi.org/10.15468/klkyl>
- MacGowan I., Barták M., Kubik Š. 2024 New records and an updated checklist of the family Lonchaeidae (Diptera) from Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 76 (4): 583–585.
<https://doi.org/10.71424/azb76.4.002770>
- MacGowan I., Gustad J.R. 2022 An annotated checklist of the Norwegian Lonchaeidae (Diptera, Cyclorrhapha) with the description of a new species. *Norwegian Journal of Entomology* 69: 284–303.
- Mendel Z., Halperin J. 1982 The biology and behavior of *Orthotomicus erosus* in Israel. *Phytoparasitica* 10 (3): 169–181.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02994526>
- Negrobov O., Naglis S. 2016 Palaearctic species of the genus *Medetera* (Diptera: Dolichopodidae). *Zoosystematica rossica* 25 (2): 333–379.
<https://doi.org/10.31610/zsr/2016.25.2.333>
- Negrobov O., Stackelberg A.A. 1969 Dolichopodidae. In: Stackelberg A.A., Narchuk E.P. (eds) *Keys to the Insects of the European Part of the USSR, Volume 5, Part 1*. Nauka, Leningrad, pp. 670–752. (In Russian)
- Parent O. 1938 Diptères Dolichopodidés. *Faune de France* 35: 1–720.
- Pollet M., Ivković M. 2018 Dolichopodidae of riverbeds and springs in Croatia with an updated checklist of Croatia (Diptera). *Zootaxa* 4455 (3): 401–428.
- Pollet M., Meuffels H. 2023 Distribution atlas of Netherlands long-legged flies (Diptera: Dolichopodidae). EIS Knowledge Centre for Insects and Other Invertebrates, Leiden, 344 pp.
- Stackelberg A.A. 1970 Family Lonchaeidae. In: Bei-Bienko G.J. (ed.) *Key to the insects of the European part of the USSR. Diptera. Vol. 5, Part 2*. Leningrad, pp. 358–373. (In Russian)
- Wermelinger B. 2002 Development and distribution of predators and parasitoids during two consecutive years of an *Ips typographus* (Col., Scolytidae) infestation. *Journal of Applied Entomology* 126 (10): 521–527.
-